

Expert evaluation questionnaire + aggregated results (n=2)

The paper's evaluation corresponds to an expert-based assessment with two experts who applied the method independently and answered a 5-point Likert questionnaire (1=Strongly disagree, 5=Strongly agree).

1. Expert profile

Expert	Experience	Primary areas
E1	5+ years	Software architecture, application security
E2	5+ years	Architecture, security engineering, requirements modeling

2. Likert items

ID	Statement
L1	Clarity of the method and its steps
L2	Ease of application (without additional support)
L3	Support for identifying relevant ZT concerns
L4	Support for maintaining ASR-QA-ZT-scenario traceability
L5	Usefulness for designing/justifying architectural decisions

3. Responses per expert

Item	E1	E2
L1	4	5
L2	4	4
L3	5	4
L4	5	5
L5	4	5

4. Aggregated results (n=2)

Item	Median	Min	Max
L1	4.5	4	5
L2	4.0	4	4
L3	4.5	4	5
L4	5.0	5	5
L5	4.5	4	5

Summary: the median per item is ≥ 4 in all cases, consistent with the statement in the paper.

5. Open questions (for replication)

- Which part of the method was most useful and why?
- Which part was most challenging and why?
- What would you improve to ease adoption in a real project?